

26-29 SEPTEMBER
2022

ISBN 978-629-97531-4-8

**THE INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
on Social Sciences
and Humanities**

Re-Humanizing the Society:

**The Role of Social Sciences
and Humanities in Nation
Building**

**The International
Conference on
Education (ICE) 2022**

PROCEEDINGS

In conjunction with

**The International
Conference on Social
Sciences and Humanities
(TICSSH) 2022**

27 – 28 SEPTEMBER 2022

Theme:

**Education for 21st
Century Learning**

Editor:

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EFFECTIVELY PROMOTING DATA-DRIVEN LEADERSHIP AMONG EDUCATION LEADERS

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ABSTRACT - The school leader's role has become more challenging and complex. Principals face demands that request them to adapt continuously. Leadership demands need to be met in an era of continuous change, which is becoming harder and harder each year with the new challenges faced by school leaders. As a result, school leaders must utilize data from national accountability measures and other data resources accurately and appropriately in order to improve student achievement and progress. However, school leaders have access to various data resources. Not enough insights are gleaned from this data, creating a gap that is very clear when we see how school leaders benefit from the available data sources. This illustrates the importance of making educational leadership programs more relevant to data-driven leadership models. This research uses a scoping review method, which is a qualitative research methodology. The researcher scoped relevant published papers based on criteria to explore what is known from existing literature. This scoping review will follow the described steps by the Joanna Briggs Institute (Munn et al., 2022). Through scoping the literature, the researcher determined a group of factors and themes about the best resources and practices implemented by school leaders and successful projects in achieving data-driven leadership. Thus, these factors could effectively promote data-driven leadership among education leaders and can help to mind the gap. Future research should be conducted to gain a more comprehensive understanding of all the factors worldwide which affect this process, including a more diverse literature data set.

Keywords: Data-Driven Instruction (DDI); Data-Driven Decision Making (DDDM); Data-Driven Leadership; Scoping review.

1. INTRODUCTION

The school leaders' role has become more challenging and complex. According to Hoyle et al. (2005), school leaders have had access to a vast amount of data recently, but more insights should be gleaned from this data, creating a noticeable gap when we see how school leaders benefit from these data sources. Moreover, school leaders, teachers, and parents have issues and dislike how data is used in education, as stated by Selwyn (2018). Data now is creating a heavy burden on students to achieve results based on national data or anticipated worldwide results but not their actual level, which is transferred to teachers and school leaders. However, data is increasingly woven into the education system, showing how much positive effect it can have when used mindfully and insightfully. This illustrates the importance of making educational leadership programs more relevant to data-driven leadership models. Data-Driven Leadership was defined by Corsair (2017) as a commitment to using data to connect businesses with their customers, drive measurement and accountability, and guide resource allocation. Thus, this research is essential to discover how to effectively promote data-driven Leadership among education leaders and gather information about the best resources and practices used to achieve this goal from successful programs and schools. Also, school leaders should be taught how to experiment and learn from local and international real-life data to meet their schools' specific needs.

2. OBJECTIVES

The research objectives are:

- a) To scope literature for the main themes that corresponds to achieving data-driven leadership.
- b) To effectively promote data-driven leadership among education leaders.

3. METHODOLOGY

The qualitative Research Method used in this research is scoping review, the researcher scoped relevant published papers to explore what is known from existing literature about the main themes and points needed to achieve data-driven decision making (DDDM) and Data-driven instructions (DDI), this scoping review follows the described steps by the Joanna Briggs institute Munn et al. (2022), where the first step is to setup a protocol that pre-defines the research objective and the methods that will be used, secondly stating research objectives and questions clearly, thirdly, scoping existence literature following a set of established criteria, fourthly, the researcher searched more than one database, such as, Google scholar database, fifthly, the researcher conducted level one screening, which means screening the titles and the abstracts, sixthly the researcher moved to level two screening, where the researchers screened the full text of the chosen papers from the previous step, seventhly, the researchers chart the collected data and then presented the collected data in the form of a table, Eighthly, the collected qualitative data will be coded and organized into themes so then they can be represented and analyzed, this will lead to the ninth step, where the researcher reached to interpretations and conclusions that can be shared with education leaders and government agencies. The researcher considered ethical aspects of research when conducting data collection through the process of analyzing data up to the point of sharing conclusions and recommendations, such as, scoping high quality literature, being bias when collecting data, and lastly sharing results.

Figure 1. The Scoping review steps.

Number	criteria	Range
1	Date of publish	2017-2022
2	Publication Type	Books, indexed published papers.
3	Subject	Data-Driven Leadership in education
4	Paper Language	English only.

Table 1. The criteria used to include and exclude scientific papers used in your review

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Scoping the literature has revealed that improving data-driven leadership and achieving a data-driven environment applies to implementing certain factors and themes stated and discussed in the scoped literature. These aspects can be categorized into the following main points: First, improving school leaders' and teachers' capacities in data collecting, analysis, and interpretation, which could be achieved through professional development opportunities and data-centered coaching programs that can be delivered through school instructional coaches. Secondly, creating a data-driven culture that endorses data usage, data usage purpose, and data literacy has been achieved in most projects and schools that showed signs of successful data integrations in the scoped literature, which shows its importance.

Thirdly, providing training and support on how to use and analyze data, focusing on practical applications and case studies. Fourthly, connecting data to a maturity model so it can be assessed and supported. Fifthly, providing technological infrastructure and hardware, as the literature states, the readiness to use data and work with it is crucial to school leaders' success. Sixthly, providing local data and creating systems to timely access and share data. Seventhly, external resources and expertise can provide better solutions and a broader perspective. Providing schools with the needed support and expertise to improve their data-driven usage and skills, and eighthly, focusing on the deeper meaning of data and how to achieve equity, not only the data collection and analysis parts. These findings show that achieving a data-driven environment in schools is a challenging task and that leaders and ministries of education need to collaborate.

The scoped literature presented the previous eight factors as dominant with all projects that established successful and impactful data-driven leadership. Furthermore, other factors were also present but at a lesser frequency, such as the leader's attributes and personal character, which could have a positive or a negative effect on implementing data-driven models. The researcher believes that this could be related to the school leader's ability to adopt new changes and adapt to new changes. However, the researcher still thinks this could be solved by implementing a systematic change model to facilitate this change process and support the leader in his efforts. Other factors are presented in the literature, which presents the need for a deeper dive to gain a more diverse and profound understanding.

5. CONCLUSION

The researcher concludes that improving and promoting data-driven leadership among school leaders can be achieved by implementing certain aspects stated and discussed in the scoped literature. With the exception that some of these aspects are not internal to the school environment, thus, achieving these aspects needs the collaboration of government agencies, ministries of education, and the private sector. Moreover, education is a very complex

system. Therefore, data-driven leadership should not just focus on technology or data analysis but also on mindful insights that place the student at its center.

6. IMPLICATION

The scoped factors have helped successful leaders to achieve data-driven leadership and, therefore, can improve other school leaders' data-driven leadership, which will influence their ability to meet the specific needs of their schools. This research recommends using the previous eight factors to create a data-driven environment that fosters school leaders to be impactful data-driven leaders. These efforts should not be an internal effort only. External resources and partners must have an active role in these reformations. Moreover, more profound research should be conducted to gain a more comprehensive understanding of all the factors worldwide that affect this process.

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